

DEVELOPMENT AND TESTING OF A HYBRIDE ACTIVE – PASSIVE ACOUSTIC SHM SYSTEM FOR IMPACT DAMAGE DETECTION IN HONEYCOMB AIRCRAFT STRUCTURES

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1 Introduction

Due to their contributions for weight reduction, the percentage of composite structural parts in commercial aircraft is continuously increasing. Still the full potential of the composite materials has not been reached, mainly due to uncertainties in the manufacturing process, the presence of barely visible impact damages (BVID's) and the prediction of the long term behavior in use, leading to much higher safety factors compared to metals to date. The effect of impact damages on the strengths of composite materials was studied intensively in the literature [1]. It was shown that impact damages of a size of 200 to 300 mm² in 3 mm CFRP panels (BVID's) lead to a reduction of approximately 30% of the compression strength.

The use of online Structural Health Monitoring (SHM) systems could help to reduce these uncertainties in the prediction of the behavior of CFRP structures and subsequently lead to tailored inspection intervals. In addition weight reduction by design optimization (including SHM in the Design process) due to enhanced life time predictability of the components and by the reduction of redundancies in the structure by monitoring difficult or impossible to inspect parts is another great potential for this new technology. Worldwide activities in the field of „Structural Health Monitoring“ are continuously growing since more than two decades. An intensive overview of the various activities in the field of structural health monitoring can be found in [2] and [3]. It is possible to classify the different technologies by the used sensor principles or by the used SHM methodologies. The most promising sensor principles are based on piezoelectric materials, eddy current foils and fiber optic sensors like fiber Bragg

grating sensors, extrinsic fabry perot interferometers or brillouin optical time domain reflectometry sensors. Analyses show that mainly the acoustic methods either passive as acoustic emission [4, 5] or active as lamb waves [6, 7] are able to cover larger areas with a sufficient size of detectable damage.

Within this work the authors present the recent results for damage detection, localization and quantification in composite honeycomb aircraft structures using a hybrid active – passive acoustic SHM system using the techniques of acoustic emission and guided ultrasonic wave in sparse array configuration.

2 Investigated Components

For the validation of the system described in chapter 3 a flat honeycomb panel of 800 x 800 x 48 mm² has been used. The used materials and lay up for the face sheet and the honeycomb core have been taken from a spoiler of an Airbus A340 aircraft which is one possible application of the hybrid active – passive acoustic SHM system shown schematically in figure 1. The body is a CFRP sandwich construction with a honeycomb core. Two different core densities are used, the spoiler body being reinforced inside with a

Figure 1: Sketch of an A340 spoiler

48kg/m³ core and the center hinge fitting (CHF) with a 32kg/m³ core. The spoiler body core is divided into three sections. The center section is oriented with its L-direction perpendicular to the hinge line, whereas the other sections and the CHF core are oriented with their L-direction parallel to the hinge line. The CFRP skins consist basically of 6 UD plies with an orientation of [-45/45/0/90/45/-45] on each side. This standard laminate is reinforced in the area of the attachment fittings as well as on the front spar with fabric 2x2 twill fabric. The reinforcement of the C-spar in the failsafe area is implemented using UD plies. The center hinge fitting (CHF) is molded via resin transfer molding (RTM).

The material properties of the used honeycomb panel (face sheet material and honeycomb core) are summarized in table 1. The elastic properties of the face sheet material have been later used to calculate the group velocities of the ultrasonic waves.

3 System Description

3.1 Concept

A predefined number of piezo-electric transducers were glued on the component in the area that should be inspected. The transducers were used for the detection of the ultrasonic waves caused either by the release of acoustic emission events directly during the occurrence of impact events or actuated by one or more of the transducers. Each transducer was used as an actuator to introduce an ultrasonic burst signal of predefined frequency and duration. In a first step each actuator was actuated and all sensors measured the acoustic response of the structure in the undamaged state giving the baseline ultrasonic signature of the structure that was used later to assess the severity of the damage.

Table 1: Material properties of face sheet and core

UD face sheet material				
E_{\parallel} [GPa]	114.7	$R_{\parallel+}$ [MPa]	1670	
E_{\perp} [GPa]	7.4	$R_{\parallel-}$ [MPa]	855	
$G_{\perp\parallel}$ [GPa]	4.8	$R_{\perp+}$ [MPa]	55	
$G_{\perp\perp}$ [GPa]	2.5	$R_{\perp-}$ [MPa]	170	
$\nu_{\perp\parallel}$	0.22	R_{shear} [MPa]	70	
$\nu_{\perp\perp}$	0.35			
Nomex core (HRH 10 48 kg/m ³)				
E_{11} / E_{22} [MPa]	E_{33} [MPa]	G_{12} [MPa]	G_{23} [MPa]	G_{13} [MPa]
1	138	1	19	31

Once the baseline measurement was done the system was switched in the passive mode – that means that all sensors were active to capture the signals in case of impact damage. The signals captured in case of an impact were used to locate the damage by triangulation – usually used in acoustic emission analyses. Special algorithms were used to take into account potential un-isotropic wave propagation in composite structures as described in more detail in chapter “Algorithms” [8]. Once the location of the impact was assessed the system was switched in active mode and the ultrasonic signature of the structure was measured using the same procedure as for the baseline measurement. The individual signals from the measurement after the impact were subtracted from the baseline signals. These residual signals were fed in an imaging algorithm – virtual near field beam forming in actuation and sensing [8] giving a 2D image of the area around the position of the damage assessed before (see chapter “Algorithms”). The energy of the residuum around the position of the impact was used to assess the severity of the damage.

3.2 Hardware

The following system was used to measure the acoustic response of the structure: data acquisition in passive and active operation was done by two 4 channel acoustic emission cards (type PCI-DISP-4 from PAC) and the actuation in active mode was done by an arbitrary waveform generator card (type: ARB-1410 from PAC) which is actuated by 3-sine burst with a sine envelope of a voltage of 100 Vpp. The used transducers – actuators and sensors – were of type smart layer sensor from Acellant. All

Fig. 2: Measurement set-up during the testing of a honeycomb panel (800 x 800 mm²) typically used for aircraft application

acquired signals are amplified with preamplifiers of type PAC WD with an amplification of 40 dB. Figure 2 shows the whole measurement set-up during the testing of a honeycomb panel (800 x 800 mm²) typically used for aircraft application (Airbus A-340 spoiler from FACC). Data acquisition in passive and active mode was realized by a Lab-view code that allows the automated actuation of different types of wave forms at adjustable center frequencies and the automated collection of raw data from the sensors together with the required meta data such as geometry of the test article, positions of the actuators and sensors, conditions during the measurement (temperature and humidity), which are used later on by the post processing software.

4 Wave propagation in thin walled composite structures

The investigated components are made of honeycomb panels covered by thin face sheets on both sides. In order to detect defects in such structures by either active or passive acoustic methods the characteristic of the propagating acoustic waves are very important. As the typical thicknesses of the face sheets, where the acoustic wave will mainly propagate are smaller than the wavelengths of these acoustic waves, these waves are confined and called therefore guided waves or lamb waves. These waves result out of the superposition of the bulk compression and shear waves and show the following characteristics:

- Different symmetric and asymmetric modes which number increase with the frequency are present in the structure
- Depending on the frequency all of these modes are more or less dispersive that means the wave velocity depend on the frequency
- When using un-isotropic composite materials the wave velocity depends on the direction of propagation
- The amplitude of the acoustic wave decrease with distance to the origin of the source due to natural wave spreading and material damping.
- Both wave spreading and damping depend on the wave mode, the frequency and in case of un-isotropic materials on the propagation direction.

For a proper placement of the sensors two properties are very important:

- The damping of the acoustic wave as it defines the maximum distance up to which an acoustic emission event can be detected before it is below the noise level
- The wave velocity as function of the direction as this parameter has to be used to locate acoustic emission events by means of triangulation or imaging algorithms.

The wave velocity (phase and group velocity) of thin walled composite structures can be calculated in all necessary direction as function of the frequency using standard software tools like DISPERSE. The results of wave velocity vs. frequency at different propagation directions for the face sheet are shown in figure 3. The necessary input data are the elastic properties summarized in table 1, the layup of [-45/45/0/90/45/-45] and the thickness of the face sheet of 0.75 mm. It can be seen that all 3 existing modes (first symmetric S0, first asymmetric A0 and the first horizontal shear mode SH0) up to this frequency depend on the propagation direction and on the frequency. The A0 mode shows the highest dispersion (variation of the group velocity with the frequency) up to a frequency of around 100 kHz and the lowest sensitivity on the propagation direction. The S0 mode is the quickest mode with rather constant group velocity up to frequency of around 400 kHz. It shows a stronger dependence on the propagation direction where the direction of quickest propagation is in 45° and -45°. This effect is expected as the double amounts of fibers exist in these two directions compared to 0° or 90°. The SH0

Fig. 3: Dispersion relation of the 3 different lamb wave modes (A0, S0 and SH0) in face sheets up to a frequency of 1 MHz

mode shows a similar behavior regarding the dependency on the propagation direction as the S0 mode.

This tool is very helpful when using active guided ultrasonic waves for damage detection as the ultrasonic signal is generated by an actuator, where the frequency can be adjusted in a defined range. In case of acoustic emission events the situation is more complex. An acoustic emission signal is typically composed of a very wide frequency spectrum, where some frequencies dominate over others. Typically it consists of a quick compression mode (S0) of higher frequencies and low amplitude followed by a slower bending mode (A0) of lower frequency and higher amplitude, illustrated in figure 4. In addition the prediction of the damping behavior based on models has high uncertainties. Therefore it is better to measure the wave propagation properties – wave velocity and damping as function of the propagation direction. For the measurement of the wave propagation properties the investigated honeycomb panel was used. The panel was equipped with a number of piezo-sensors on the circumference of the plate equally spaced (390 mm distance). The system used to measure the acoustic response of the structure has already been described in chapter 3.2. In order to simulate AE events a Hsu Nielson source (defined pencil break) was used. Pencil breaks have been done all over the plate in two different classes:

- Class 1: pencil breaks close to the sensors to assess the wave velocities
- Class 2: pencil breaks between the sensors in a rectangular raster to assess the amplitude as function of the distance and angle

Figure 5 shows a sketch of the surface of the honeycomb panel with the positions of the used

Fig. 4: Form of a typical AE signal

sensors and positions of the pencil breaks for both classes.

Prior to the performance of the pencil breaks, the noise in the laboratory was measured for a defined time of 3 minutes by activating all active sensors. The amplitude of the noise was 28 dB. During the measurement the detection threshold was set to a level of 30 dB, 2 dB over the maximum noise level. Figure 6 shows the amplitude as function of the distance and deflection angle out of the test campaign with the class 1 and class 2 pencil breaks.

It was shown that signal arising from the pencil breaks with amplitude of around 80 dB can be detected up to distances of longer than 1 m. The damping was lowest for the 45° and -45° direction and highest for the 0° and 90°. Such behavior was expected from the layup of the face sheet with double amount of carbon fibers in 45° and -45° direction. Out of the damping characteristic AE events of 80 dB amplitude and higher – as usual for impacts – can be detected at a distance of around 1 m with amplitude of 40dB well above the noise level. Besides the damping of the ultrasonic waves, the wave velocity as function of the propagation angle is a very important parameter as it is required to determine the source location of the AE events and therefore the location of the defect. Passive system source location is done by triangulation using the arrival time differences between the first hit sensor, which triggers the measurement, to all other sensors. There are different methods to determine the time when a sensor is hit. The most common

Fig. 5: Sketch of the surface of the honeycomb panel with the positions of the used sensors and positions of the pencil breaks for both classes

method is to use the first time, when a signal is crossing the threshold. In this case always the quickest wave which is above the threshold triggers the measurement, which is in case of the honeycomb panel the S0 mode of the face sheet. As always the quickest wave is used, no problems can arise from reflections on the boundaries. On the other hand as already shown in figure 4, the quick mode has lower amplitudes compared to the bending modes (A0 mode). Therefore at higher distances this mode can be lower than the threshold leading to wrong location information. Figure 7 shows the evaluated wave velocities as function of the distance out of the class 1 pencil breaks. It can be seen that the scatter of the calculated wave velocities increases with the distance and depend on the propagation direction. The most close wave velocities are in 45° direction, which shows also the lowest damping and for the 0° and 90° in a distance of 400 mm. The reason for the strong scatter in wave velocity at higher distances arises from the too strong damping of the S0 mode. Therefore the threshold crossing came from other slower modes.

5 Algorithms

Two different algorithms were used. A localization algorithm for the determination of the source location of the impact based on the signals acquired during the impact by the passive part of the system and a virtual beam forming algorithm around the position of the impact based on the signals acquired after the occurrence of the impact by the active part of the system.

Fig. 6: Amplitude as function of the distance and propagation angle out of the test campaign with the class 1 and class 2 pencil breaks

5.1 Localization by Triangulation

The method used for localization is based on triangulation using the arrival time differences of the measured AE signal by the individual sensors. Conventional AE systems assume a constant wave velocity in all directions. In such a case the number of all points on a plate showing the same arrival time differences is a hyperbole. If more than 2 sensors are used, the each sensor pair results in a specific hyperbole and the intersections of the different hyperboles give the source location. In case of unisotropic wave propagation, as it is the case for the investigated honeycomb panel and the layup of the face sheets, this approach leads to errors. In dependence of the shape of the wave front analytic solutions may exist. If the wave propagates in the shape of a square with the highest wave velocity in the direction of the fibers as it is approximately the case in [0/90] layups in GFRP [8] the problem can be described in the so called “Manhattan Metric”, where the wave propagated only along the fiber directions and the distance between two points is given by the sum of the absolute differences of the individual coordinates and independent from the propagation path. The place of all points having a fixed arrival time difference between two sensors is a straight line. If the sensors are placed on the edges of a rectangular parallel to the fiber orientation the line is orientated normal to the connection line between the sensors where the position of this straight line depends on the arrival time difference between the two sensors as shown for sensor 1 and sensor 2 having the same y coordinate in the equation (1) and for sensors 1 and 3 having the same

Fig. 7: Evaluated wave velocities as function of the distance out of the class 1 pencil breaks

x coordinate in equation (2):

$$x_{Source} = \frac{x_1 + x_2}{2} - \frac{v \cdot \Delta t_{1 \rightarrow 2}}{2} \quad (1)$$

$$y_{Source} = \frac{y_1 + y_3}{2} - \frac{v \cdot \Delta t_{1 \rightarrow 3}}{2} \quad (2)$$

where x_i and y_i are the coordinates of the sensors “i”, v is the wave velocity and $\Delta t_{i \rightarrow j}$ is the arrival time difference between sensor “i” and sensor “j”.

In case of the used face sheet the shape of the wave front lays between the two cases described before. For the localization of the impacts the following approach has been used. In a first step the damage location will be assessed based on isotropic wave propagation. Once this first approximation of the position has been determined, only sensors with a maximum distance of 0.5 m from this position will be used. The limitation of the nearest sensors is necessary, as higher distances lead to too strong damping of the S0 mode which was used for localization. Once this first approximation of the impact position has been performed, the second location algorithm is used to determine a second approximation of the impact position. The impact position is finally calculated by both positions using the average coordinates of both approximations.

5.2 Virtual Beam Forming

As the backscattered signals from defects are typically small compared to the reflections from the boundaries and the characteristic of the travelling lamb waves is complex no simple interpretation of the data taken only from a damaged structure is possible. Therefore the acoustic response of the structure (collected signals from all sensors for all active actuators) will be measured before (baseline measurement) and after the appearance of damages and compared against each other. The comparison was done by a subtraction of the individual transient signals before and after the occurrence of the damage. The difference signals are the basis for damage detection, localization and quantification. Therefore any change in the transient signals between the baseline measurement and the measurement after the occurrence of damage beside that caused by the damage itself could lead to misinterpretations. Figure 1 illustrates the effect of the temperature on the measured signal at a distance

of 150 mm from an actuator actuated by 3 sin burst with a center frequency of 60 kHz. When comparing the measurements at different temperatures the following conclusions can be drawn: the higher the temperature difference, the larger the difference between the two signals; the wave velocities and the damping of the travelling lamb waves change with temperature – the higher the temperature, the lower the wave velocity and the higher the damping (see Figure 8) and the effect is larger when the actuation frequency is higher. The average wave velocity change / temperature is in the range of 1.7 (m/s)/K for the A0 mode at 60 kHz and 0.22 (m/s)/K for the S0 mode at 250 kHz. The influences seem to be low but produce remarkable difference signals if the signals will be subtracted from each other. Therefore the influence of the environment and especially the temperature that lead to changes in the amplitude and wave speed are critical and need to be minimized to reduce their influences on the results. The following steps were used in the post processing algorithm. In a 1st step the raw data from all piezo sensors were filtered using an FIR (or respectively FFT) band pass filter to remove the noise and direct current content. In a 2nd step the filtered signals coming from two different measurements – baseline measurement and measurement after the introduction of the impact are compared to each other in order to compensate environmental effects. The maximum measured amplitudes of the individual filtered signal will be normalized to a value of 1. In a 3rd step the frequency response of the individual signals will be compared and the frequency spectrum of the measurement after the

Fig. 8: Measured transient signals from a piezo sensor at 150 mm distance from the piezo actuator at different temperatures

damage will be shifted to higher or lower frequencies to achieve a minimum standard deviation with respect to the baseline measurement. This frequency shift algorithm aims to compensate differences in propagation speed. The 4th step is used to visualize the results by transferring the filtered and corrected transient signals from the time domain to the 2-dimensional space domain. Therefore a near-field beam forming algorithm was used as shown schematically in figure 9. The algorithm is based on the time-of-flight principle. First part is to define a mesh of planar coordinates (x, y) over the plate. For each position the distance to the corresponding actuator $I_{aj}(x, y)$ and sensor $I_{sj}(x, y)$ is calculated. Assuming fixed propagation speeds c_A in actuation and c_S in sensing the distances are transformed into time delays ($t_{sj}(x, y)c_s / t_{aj}(x, y)c_a$). Two different propagation speeds in actuation and sensing are introduced to be able to account for mode conversion at the defect position. With the known central time of actuation the corresponding time of observation t_{obs} , where a reflection would be observed for the coordinates x and y, is calculated by $t_{obs} = t_{offset} + t_{sj}(x, y)c_s + t_{aj}(x, y)c_a$. For each combination of sensors and actuators and each position the time of observation is calculated. A time window with time dilation of the corresponding wavelet is centered around t_{obs} . This signal window is windowed by a hamming window to smooth the signal. These windows, which inherently contain the near-field steering delays for both actuation and sensing arrays, are simply added. In this step the

Fig. 9: Illustration of the near field beam forming algorithm in sparse array configuration

delay-and-sum beam forming applies. Hence for each position a beam formed signal window is obtained, which is used to calculate the squared power sum, breaking down the signal vector into a scalar, which gives information about the reflectivity at this position. All mentioned steps described above were implemented in a MatLab code that allows an automated evaluation of the raw data collected by the system described in chapter 3.2.

5 Results

In order to prove the damage detection, localization and quantification different types of tests have been performed. In a first step non damaging impacts have been introduced over the honeycomb panel to demonstrate the damage location ability of the passive part of the system. In a second step different weights have been placed at the same positions as the simulated impacts to simulate damages and prove the damage localization and quantification ability of the active part of the system. Finally real impacts have been introduced in the panel by a drop tower to prove the whole system performance. Figure 10 show the overview of logic of the impact test campaign. The test campaign was organized in such a way that it was possible to assess the repeatability of the individual measurements on a short term and long term basis including effects of slight temperature variations between the different tests.

5.1 Simulated Impacts

Non damaging impacts have been used to assess the localization ability of the passive part of the system. A small cylinder with a spherical head with a mass

Fig. 10: Logic of the whole test campaign

of 100 g was used. The impactor was dropped from a height of around 10 cm producing impacts of incident energy of around 0.1 J well below any damaging effect. The positions of the non-damaging impacts are the same as for the class 2 pencil breaks used for the assessment of the damping behavior illustrated in figure 5. Both mentioned localization procedures described in paragraph 5.1 have been used to locate the impact positions. Figure 11 illustrates both localization algorithms where the blue lines show the intersecting hyperboles assuming a circular wave front and the red lines show the intersection of straight lines assuming a square wave front. Both localization algorithms show no single intersection point but an area of all intersection points. The center of all intersection point gave the position of the impact. When comparing both localization algorithms for this specific impact both localization algorithms gave similar results, where slight lower localization errors were achieved for the assumption of a circular shaped wave front. Both localization procedures were used to assess all positions of the non-damaging impact and the localization error was calculated for all positions. Figure 12 illustrates the located impacts over the honeycomb panel using both triangulation procedures – green dots for the real impact position, red squares for the isotropic localization and blue squares for the orthotropic

Figure 11: Illustration of both localization algorithms: blue lines show the intersecting hyperboles assuming a circular wave front, red lines show the intersection straight lines assuming a square wave front; the red dot shows the impact position

localization. The maximum localization error was about 120 mm and the average localization error was around 34 mm over all non-damaging impacts in case of the algorithm assuming the circular wave front. The same assessment has been performed using the triangulation algorithm assuming a square shaped wave front. The evaluation of the results showed that the maximum and average localization error was around 113 mm and 54 mm respectively using this approach. Although the wave front is not a strict circle (see also figure 7) it is more close to a circle compared to a square. It was therefore expected that the triangulation method using a constant wave speed will lead to better results. Therefore this method will also be used later on to locate the real impacts.

5.2 Simulated Defects

Prior to the introduction of the real impacts, the active part of the system together with the near field beam forming algorithm was proven by placing defined weights on the non-damaging impact positions (see figure 7). A cylindrical disc of 50 mm in diameter with a total weight of 600 g was used. The used test logic was comparable to the impact test campaign illustrated in figure 9 except that no passive impact detection was performed during the placement of the weight at different positions. Similar to the impact test campaign baseline

Fig. 12: Localization of the non-damaging impacts on the honeycomb panels (green dots for the real impact position, red squares for the isotropic localization and blue squares for the orthotropic localization)

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measurements and measurements after the placement of the weight have been performed several times to prove the repeatability of the measurement and to assess the influence of small changes in the environment – mainly the temperature – during the different measurement campaigns. For actuation a Morlet Wavelet with approximately 3 periods has been used. This waveform has been chosen as it gives reasonable resolution in both the time and frequency domain. The resolution in the time domain is important to avoid overlapping signals. On the other hand very short burst signals lead to broadband frequency spectra. Especially in the high dispersive frequency range of the propagating waves (frequency up to around 80 kHz for A0 mode and frequencies higher than 700 kHz for the S0 mode) broadband signals lead to strong wave spreading and subsequent strong overlapping of the propagating waves especially at higher distances. Seven center frequencies from 20 kHz up to 200 kHz in 30 kHz steps have been used. Each transducer was used as actuator and all other transducer are used to receive the signals. Once all data from the different measurement campaigns have been collected all were fed in the virtual beam

forming algorithm described in chapter 5.2. Figure 13 shows the graphical user interface (GUI) of the post processing algorithms with a typical result of damage detection. The post processing algorithms is able to compare different baseline and impact measurements at a given frequency. Each possible combination of actuators and sensors can be used to generate the 2D acoustic image of the structure including the minimization of environmental effects by the mentioned frequency shift method. In the experiment shown in figure 13 the weight was placed at the position: $x = 0.6$ m $y = -0.2$ m of the used coordinate system. All actuators and sensors where used to reconstruct the acoustic response of the structure at an actuation frequency of 80 kHz using the A0 mode for the reconstruction. Two baseline and two damage measurements were used in the shown analyses. The left and the middle figure show the distribution of the residuum signal and the standard deviation between 1 baseline measurement and of 1 measurement after the placement of the weight using the best suited baseline (closest temperature difference between the baseline and the measurement after the placement of the weight). The right figure shows the standard deviation between

Fig. 13: View of the GUI of the near field beam forming algorithm together with the 2D images of the residual signals between baseline measurements and measurements after the placement of the weight at position (0.6 m / -0.2 m) using an actuation frequency of 80 kHz reconstructed with a velocity of 750 m/s corresponding to the A0 mode in actuation and sensing

the average of the 2 baseline measurements and the average of the two measurements taken after the placement of the sensors. It could be clearly seen that the location of the weight can be located in both cases, where better localization results were achieved for the case of best suited baseline. In summary it can be concluded that the weight can be detected and located at various positions on the honeycomb panel using the A0 mode for damage detection up to a frequency of 80 kHz. The localization of the simulated damage is less clear compared to the passive part of the system. Figure 14 shows the results achieved by the reconstruction of the A0 mode at 50 kHz for two positions of the weight. The localization accuracy when using the S0 mode at frequencies of 110 kHz and higher for reconstruction is less good compared to the reconstruction with the A0 mode.

5.3 Impact Damage Detection

Finally the performance of the active passive system together with the passive localization and the active virtual beam forming algorithms was proven by the detection of impacts in the honeycomb panel. Two different impacts of 15.3J and 19.2J have been introduced at the positions $x = 590 \text{ mm} / y = -195 \text{ mm}$ and $x = 300 \text{ mm} / y = 130 \text{ mm}$. Therefore a spherical impactor of 40 mm diameter with different additional weights was dropped from different heights of 500 mm and 1000 mm producing impact damages with overall damage areas of 300 mm^2 and 600 mm^2 . The overall damage sizes have been measured by conventional ultrasonic scanning of the damaged area. Prior to the introduction of the impacts several baseline measurements have been performed. During the introduction of the impacts

Fig. 14: Results achieved by the reconstruction of the A0 mode at 50 kHz for two positions (white circles) of the weight.

the system was switched in passive mode to locate the impact positions. After the introduction of the impact the acoustic response of the structure has been measured several times and compared to the different baseline measurements to assess the severity of the damage. Figure 15 shows the located impacts during the introduction of both impacts using the passive part of the system (upper part) and the residuum between the measurement after the introduction of the first 15.3 J impact and the baseline measurement (right lower part) and the

Figure 15: Located impacts during the introduction of both impacts by the passive part of the system (upper part) and residuum between the measurement after the introduction of the first 15.3 J impact and the baseline measurement (right lower part) and residuum between the measurement after the introduction of the second 19.2 J impact and the introduction of the first 15.3 J impact (left lower part) using the active part of the system for image reconstruction by the A0 mode at 80 kHz

residuum between the measurement after the introduction of the second 19.2 J impact and the introduction of the first 15.3 J impact (left lower part). Both impacts could be detected with a location error of less than 10 mm using the passive part of the system together with the localization algorithm assuming a constant propagation velocity. The measured energy of the AE event was around 12.8×10^6 aJ for the 15.3J impact and around 11.3×10^6 aJ in case of the 19J impact, which was an order of magnitude higher than the non-damaging impacts used in chapter 5.1. It can be seen that the AE energy is approximately the same for both impacts and seems to be not a good measure for the quantification of the impact energy or impact damage size.

The results for the detection and localization of the impact by the active part of the system are similar to that achieved for the simulated defects by the weights described in chapter 5.2. Best results were achieved when using the A0 mode up to a maximum frequency of 110 kHz for the reconstruction of the 2D acoustic image of the honeycomb panel (lower part of figure 15 - the white circles indicate the positions of the impacts). When using the S0 mode for the reconstruction of the 2D acoustic image, the position of the impact damage could not be identified as exactly. The extension of the regions of high residuum (red color in the lower part of figure 15) scales with the incident impact energy and subsequent with the damage size. The results shown in figure 15 have been achieved using measurements for the baseline and after the introduction of the impacts with a maximum temperature difference of 1.5°C. If the temperature difference between the individual measurements was higher, the results were less clear.

6 Summary

Within this paper the authors presented a hybrid active-passive SHM system for the online detection, localization and quantification of impact damages in aeronautic composite structures. Experiments on aircraft honeycomb structures showed that the locations of the impacts could be assessed with an average location error of less than 5% relative to the average sensor spacing using the passive mode. One drawback of the passive method in damage size quantification is that once the sensors are in

saturation such as in case of high energy impacts no discrimination regarding damage size is possible. The location and the severity of the damage could be assessed when operating the system in active mode. The results in active mode depend strongly on changing environmental conditions - like temperature - between the baseline measurement and the measurement after the introduction of the impact. The results of the active part of the system were less precise in the localization of the impact position compared to the passive part. The combination of the passive and active part of the system to one hybrid system allows the detection, localization and quantification of impact damages in aeronautic composite structures.

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